

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND INFRARED DATA (cm⁻¹) OF TH_n, [MT] AND [MT.o-phen]

Compound	m.p. (°C)	%M	%N	%C	%H	ν_{N-H}	$\nu_{C=O}$	$\nu_{N \rightarrow O}$	ν_{o-phen}
TH _n	—	—	—	—	—	~3210s	~1680s	~1300m	—
ZnT (Colourless)	<250	25.55 (25.31)*	16.43 (16.25)	37.34 (37.15)	3.01 (2.70)	—	~1610s	~1235s	—
CdT (Colourless)	186-87	36.37 (36.81)	14.08 (13.75)	31.61 (31.44)	2.69 (2.29)	—	~1612s	~1235s	—
HgT (Yellow)	175-76	49.87 (50.10)	10.87 (10.67)	24.71 (24.39)	2.03 (1.78)	—	~1610s	~1938s	—
ZnT.o-phen (Yellow)	246-47	15.24 (14.97)	10.06 (10.13)	54.43 (54.71)	3.62 (3.40)	—	~1610s ~1238s	~730s	1170m
CdT.o-phen (Colourless)	165	22.79 (23.15)	14.31 (14.42)	49.65 (49.43)	3.32 (3.10)	—	~1610s ~1238s	~730s	1170m 1420m

s=strong, m=medium, * Figures in parentheses indicate calculated values.

C=O oxygen of the COO⁻ group. Bhattacharyya and Ray⁵ have argued in favour of C=O oxygen of the COO⁻ group acting as bridging atom in [CuT]_n chelate based on some X-ray crystallographic studies in similar type of complexes. Since the [CuT]_n, [ZnT]_n, [CdT]_n and [HgT]_n have same stoichiometry as well as very similar ir spectra it is believed that the C=O oxygen of COO⁻ group acts as a bridging atom. Also bridging through $N \rightarrow O$ oxygen will lead to a strained four membered ring while bridging through C=O oxygen will offer a strain free eight membered ring involving the two metal ions. Four membered rings have been found to be highly strained in tetrahedral geometry⁹ and is also likely to lead to subnormal magnetic moment in [CuT]_n through super exchange. [CuT]_n, however, shows a normal magnetic moment³ of 1.85 B.M.

The ν_{N-H} band of the ligand at ~3210 cm⁻¹ disappears and $\nu_{C=O}$ at ~1680 cm⁻¹ is lowered considerably to ~1610 cm⁻¹ in metal complexes (Table 1). $\nu_{N \rightarrow O}$ at ~1300 cm⁻¹ is also lowered to ~1235 cm⁻¹ indicating coordination through $N \rightarrow O \rightarrow M^{10}$. Zinc(II) and cadmium(II) mono-(ligand) complexes provide mixed chelates with o-phenanthroline while mono(ligand) mercury(II) chelate does not do so. Such failure of mono-(ligand) mercury(II) chelate to raise its coordination number is in tune with our earlier observations^{11,12} with monobasic bidentate and monobasic tridentate triazene-1-oxides. [ZnT.o-phen]_n, [CdT.o-phen]_n and [CuT.o-phen]_n mixed chelates have been identified by the appearance of new characteristic ir bands at ~730, ~1170 and ~1420 cm⁻¹ for coordinated o-phenanthroline^{10,11}, disappearance of ν_{N-H} , lowering of $\nu_{C=O}$ and $\nu_{N \rightarrow O}$ bands. These mixed chelates are also insoluble in common organic solvents. A polymeric structure (cf. Fig. 1, reference 13) appears consistent with all properties¹².

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Cobalt(II) and Copper(II) Complexes with Substituted Aminobenzothiazoles, Part-II

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In a recent work¹, we reported the synthesis of a series of Hg(II) complexes with substituted aminobenzothiazoles. As an extension of the previous report, the present paper describes the preparation and characterisation of Co(II) and Cu(II) complexes with monodentate 2-amino-6-methyl benzothiazole and 2-amino-6-chlorobenzothiazole.

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NOTES

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS, CONDUCTANCE, MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY AND SOME IR SPECTRAL DATA

Compounds	%Metal		%N		%S		ΔM mhos cm^2	μ_{eff} B.M.	$\nu(C-S)$
	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.			
$[CoL_2Cl_2]$	12.82	12.87	12.12	12.23	13.82	13.98	10.5	4.42	800
$[CoL'_2Cl_2]$	11.68	11.82	11.12	11.23	12.76	12.83	11.8	4.50	805
$[CoL_2Br_2]$	10.60	10.77	10.10	10.24	11.58	11.70	15.5	4.40	795
$[CoL_2(SCN)_2]$	10.72	10.81	15.30	15.42	23.34	23.50	18.0	4.64	800
$[CoL'_2(ClO_4)_2]$	5.80	5.92	11.16	11.25	12.76	12.85	225.0	4.40	805
$[CuL_2Cl_2]$	13.64	13.74	12.00	12.12	13.70	13.85	20.0	1.78	810
$[CuL'_2Cl_2]$	12.50	12.63	11.04	11.13	12.58	12.72	12.5	1.80	810
$[CuL_2(OAc)_2]$	12.32	12.47	10.82	10.99	12.48	12.56	10.8	1.75	805
$[CuL_2(NO_3)_2]$	12.20	12.33	15.12	16.29	12.28	12.42	12.5	1.85	800
$[CuL'_2(NO_3)_2]$	11.28	11.42	14.98	15.10	11.32	11.50	13.0	1.75	805
$[CuL'_2(ClO_4)_2]$	6.28	6.35	11.04	11.19	12.64	12.79	230.0	1.80	800

L=2-Amino-6-methyl benzothiazole, L'=2-Amino-6-chlorobenzothiazole.

Experimental

The substituted amino-benzothiazoles have been synthesised by standard procedure².

Preparation of the complexes: Methanolic solution of the metal salts were reacted separately with methanolic solution of the substituted amino benzothiazoles (1 : 2 ratio) and refluxed for about one hour. Crystalline compounds separated out on cooling. These were filtered, washed with methanol followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*.

Metal contents in the complexes were estimated complexometrically by EDTA method and nitrogen and sulphur by standard procedure. Conductance was measured in $10^{-3}M$ acetone solution using Toshniwal conductivity bridge. IR spectra were recorded in KBr phase using Unicam SP-1025 spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra of the complexes in chloroform solution were recorded using Hilger Watt Uvispeck spectrophotometer. Data are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The complexes reported are of the compositions $[M(L \text{ or } L')_2X_2]$ and $[ML'_2Y_2]$, where M=Co(II), Cu(II); L=2-amino-6-methyl benzothiazole; L'=2-amino-6-chlorobenzothiazole; X=Cl⁻, Br⁻, SCN⁻, NO₃⁻, OAc⁻ and Y=ClO₄⁻. All the cobalt complexes are blue in colour and the copper complexes are light green to dirty green in colour. The complexes have low melting points and are soluble in acetone in which medium they are found to be non-electrolytes (except perchlorate complexes), ΔM being in the range of 10-20 mhos. cm^2 ; the ΔM of perchlorate complexes are found to be around 230 mhos. cm^2 , indicating 1 : 2 electrolytic nature of these complexes.

The study of ir spectra shows the appearance of a sharp peak $\sim 815 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the free ligands which can be assigned¹ to $\nu(C-S)$ vibrations and on complexation this frequency has been shifted down to lower frequency region $\sim 800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating the bonding of benzothiazole molecule to metal ions through ring sulphur atom. The bands observed³ around 1535 cm^{-1} and $\sim 3250 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the free

ligands are due to $\nu(C=N)$ and $\nu(N-H)$ vibrations respectively, but no change of these bands has been noticed in the complexes which conclusively proves that both the endo- and exo-cyclic nitrogen atoms are not bonded to the metal ions. The thiocyanato complexes have two sharp bands $\sim 2080 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 735 cm^{-1} attributable^{4,5} to $\nu(C\equiv N)$ and $\nu(C-S)$ vibrations respectively of N-bonded terminal thiocyanato group. In the present case, an increase of $30-40 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ relative to the free thiocyanate ion is indicative of N-bonded terminal thiocyanate group on the basis of earlier observations⁶. In the nitrate complexes, absorption bands appear in the region ~ 1280 and 1400 cm^{-1} . The position of ν_4 and ν_1 and their separation ($\Delta\nu$) of $\sim 120 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggests⁷⁻⁹ the nitrate group to be monodentate in the two copper complexes. In the perchlorate complex a broad hump appears in the $1040-1150 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region indicating¹⁰⁻¹² the presence of ionic perchlorate group which is corroborated with the conductance data of the complexes. In sodium acetate two sharp peaks are observed^{11,13} at 1578 cm^{-1} and 1414 cm^{-1} region. In the present case, two sharp peaks appeared at 1645 cm^{-1} and 1410 cm^{-1} , which can be assignable to $\nu_{as} \text{ COO}^-$ and $\nu_s \text{ COO}^-$ vibrations.

Magnetic susceptibility measurements indicate the presence of three unpaired electrons in case of Co(II) and one in the Cu(II) complexes respectively. In the electronic spectra of the cobalt(II) complexes two intense bands appear at 16.0 (1450) and 8.5 (200) K.k region assignable¹⁴ to ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (P) and ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (F) transitions respectively. These two characteristic transitions, particularly the high intensity of ${}^4T_{1g}$ (P) transition and the magnetic moment values suggest the complexes to be tetrahedral. In the case of copper(II) complexes, a single band was observed in 17.0 (60) K.k region due to d-d transition. This is indicative¹⁵⁻¹⁷ of square planar configuration.

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